

Stress tolerance— excess water

Rapid and nondestructive screening technique for elongation in deepwater rice (DWR) using gibberellic acid (GA₃)

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Present techniques for assessing plant elongation ability are potentially destructive because poorly elongated rice plants die when flooded for prolonged periods.

We compared two nondestructive procedures using GA₃ treatment and short-duration flooding at seedling stage to overcome this problem. GA₃ induces the elongation response of DWR during flooding. We seeded 48 entries in two experiments in completely randomized design with three replications. Entries included modern variety (MV) nonelongating types, MV elongating types, tall traditional, tall elongating, deepwater varieties, and floating types from several countries. Plants were thinned at the 3-leaf stage and then allowed to grow.

In the first experiment, we sprayed plants at the 4-leaf stage with 500 or 1,000 ppm GA₃ at the rate of about 0.3 ml/plant. GA₃ was initially dissolved in ethyl alcohol with final concentrations of 0.05 wt/vol for the 500 ppm GA₃ and 0.1 wt/vol for the 1,000 ppm GA₃ treatment. The same ethanol concentration was used for the control.

Another complete set of the entries was submerged for 7 d at 21 d after seeding (DAS). We computed plant elongation by subtracting plant height before flooding from that after treatment.

GA₃ treatment produced no significant differences in internode length. We grouped entries into categories based on the average internode length at the 5- to 6-wk stage: good elongation (1-3), medium elongation (5), and poor elongation (7-9). Results suggest that internodes of floating rices are more sensitive to GA₃ than are those of

Plant elongation measured by plant height increase after 7 d flooding and by internode length in nonflooded plants after different doses of GA₃.

Variety	Country or origin	Plant elongation during flooding (cm)	Internode elongation (cm)			Elongation score ^a	
			GA ₃ 1000 ppm	GA ₃ 500 ppm	Av Control (no GA ₃)		
<i>Nonelongating type</i>							
Dulhabhog	Bangladesh	33	51	35	43	0	9
Safri 17	India	37	38	44	41	0	9
Jaya	India	34	38	61	49	0	9
IR5	IRRI	30	31	55	43	0	9
IR42	IRRI	28	48	45	46	0	9
Mahsuri	Malaysia	38	49	47	48	0	9
TN1	Taiwan	44	52	61	57	0	5
Av		35	44	50	47	0	
<i>Tall traditional</i>							
Ashini	Bangladesh	41	42	37	39	0	9
Rajasail	Bangladesh	44	29	43	36	0	9
Maliabanger	Bangladesh	40	40	35	37	0	9
Patnai 23	India	45	53	40	46	0	9
Manoharsali	India	38	32	38	35	0	9
NC492	India	37	31	47	39	0	9
NDGR207	India	34	36	49	43	1	9
Sugapankhi	India	30	59	42	50	0	7
Nam Sagui 19	Thailand	46	65	44	55	0	5
Av		39	43	41	42	0	
<i>Deepwater and MV elongating types</i>							
Girmi	Bangladesh	55	55	54	54	0	5
Jaisaria	Bangladesh	51	55	67	61	0	5
Bhadoia 293	Bangladesh	47	70	54	62	1	5
Bhainslot	India	58	43	57	51	0	5
NDGR150	India	45	51	80	66	0	3
IR11141-6-1-4	IRRI	42	67	92	80	0	3
IR11288-B-B-69-1	IRRI	38	57	55	56	0	5
Walihandiran	Sri Lanka	27	68	53	61	0	5
BKNFR76106-16-0-1	Thailand	11	61	70	66	0	3
RD19	Thailand	50	62	89	75	0	3
Pan Tawng	Thailand	39	47	65	56	0	5
Pin Gaew 56	Thailand	38	55	49	52	0	5
Av		42	58	65	57	0	
<i>Tall elongating type</i>							
Rayada 16-05	Bangladesh	54	58	45	51	0	5
Rayada 16-06	Bangladesh	52	56	10	63	0	5
SranKraham	Cambodia	44	53	77	65	3	3
TCA148-3	India	53	78	52	65	4	5
Chakia 59	India	52	61	80	71	8	3
IR40905-11-3-1-5-3-3	IRRI	54	73	55	64	4	5
Av		52	61	64	57	3	
<i>Floating type</i>							
Sarsari	Bangladesh	87	86	122	104	9	1
BR516-48-3	Bangladesh	80	94	111	103	26	1
Khama	Bangladesh	80	99	105	102	13	1
Bhadoia303	Bangladesh	78	123	101	112	32	1
Chamard	Bangladesh	69	75	80	78	6	3
Baishbish	Bangladesh	66	74	71	73	3	3
Digha	Bangladesh	60	90	51	70	0	3
Rayada 16-04	Bangladesh	50	87	75	81	0	1
Bazail65	Bangladesh	47	97	80	89	9	1
Vear sar	Cambodia	71	53	80	66	6	3
Anlong Phnom	Cambodia	51	51	79	65	6	5
Jalmagna	India	77	122	123	123	26	1
Chhota Bhawalia	India	68	105	98	102	16	1
LMN111	Thailand	75	92	103	98	14	1
Av		68	89	87	88	12	
Comparison		SED	LSD (0.05)				
2-mxs mean		7.51	14.88				
r ²		0.40					

^a Score for av internode length. 1 = >80 cm, 3 = 65-79 cm, 5 = 50-64 cm, and 7-9 = <50 cm.

nonfloating rices (see table). Among floating rice varieties, plants with good elongation ability were more sensitive than those with moderate ability. The r^2 values for the correlation between elongation following flooding relative to internode length with GA₃ treatment was 0.40.

The GA₃ treatment did not reflect elongation ability during submergence in some cases. Submergence-tolerant variety

BKNFR76106-16-0-1, for example, had an exceptionally high internode length of 66 cm after GA₃ treatment, but it elongated the least among entries in the flooding treatment.

Plant elongation from short-duration flooding at early seedling stage was usually comparable to that with GA₃ treatment except in cases where elongating and nonelongating MVs did not differ much from the other.

Findings suggest that plant sensitivity to GA₃ may differ between floating and nonfloating rice varieties during at least the 5-6 wk stage.

Foliar application of 500 ppm GA₃ could be used during the seedling stage to distinguish floating rices possessing good elongation ability from those having poor elongation ability and from nonfloating rices. □

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Basmati 385 approved for cultivation in Punjab, India

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Basmati 385 was introduced from Pakistan. We evaluated it in the Punjab for yield, morphological traits, grain quality, and disease and insect resistance. Basmati 385 produced about 30% more rice than Basmati 370, but it was outyielded by Pusa Basmati 1 by about 4% in research and adaptive trials.

Yield data for the varieties under different N levels and dates of transplanting (Table 1) showed that 60 kg N/ha is optimum for Basmati 385 and Basmati 370, while 90 kg N/ha is optimum for Pusa Basmati 1 under normal soil fertility. The optimum time for transplanting is the first fortnight of July

Table 1. Yield of Basmati 385, Basmati 370, and Pusa Basmati 1 under different N levels and transplanting dates, 1991 wet season.

Treatment	Yield (t/ha)		
	Basmati 385	Basmati 370	Pusa Basmati 1
N level (kg N/ha)			
0	3.2	2.1	3.5
60	4.3	3.3	4.6
90	4.3	3.2	4.9
120	4.3	3.1	5.0
Mean	4.0	3.1	4.5
Transplanting date			
15 Jun	3.9	3.1	4.4
30 Jun	4.3	3.3	4.8
15 Jul	4.1	4.2	3.8
25 Jul	3.4	2.3	3.6
Mean	4.1	3.2	4.1

for Basmati 385 and Basmati 370 and the second fortnight of June for Pusa Basmati 1.

Morphological and grain quality traits for the varieties are in Table 2. Grain shape and cooking quality of Basmati 385 are similar to those of Basmati 370. Although grains of Pusa Basmati 1 are longer and more slender than the rice of Basmati 370 and Basmati 385, cooking quality and head rice recovery of Pusa Basmati 1 is slightly inferior to that of the others. Pusa Basmati 1 received the lowest score of the three in a consumer acceptability test for cooking and eating quality of rice. Grain quality of Basmati 38.5 meets requirements for export to the Middle East, Europe, and the United States.

Basmati 385 matures earlier than Basmati 370 and Pusa Basmati 1. It has short plant height and sturdier stems than Basmati 370, but is taller than Pusa Basmati 1. The three varieties are equally susceptible to bacterial blight and stem borer, the two most serious pests of rice in the Punjab.

Krasnodarsky 86, a modern variety for use without pesticides in Kuban and Crimea, Russia

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Krasnodarsky 86 is a modern, multiple-resistant rice variety. The Russian Ministry of Agriculture released it in

Table 2. Morphological and grain quality characters of Basmati 385, Basmati 370, and Pusa Basmati 1.

Character	Basmati 385	Basmati 370	Pusa Basmati 1
Plant height (cm)	140	165	100
Days to maturity (no.)	135	150	140
Panicle-bearing tillers (no./m ²)	234	243	273
Spikelets (no./panicle)	210	140	168
Head rice recovery (%)	61.60	62.20	60.50
1000-grain wt (g)	15.80	15.70	16.50
Grain length (mm)	7.15	7.15	7.52
Grain breadth (mm)	1.65	1.63	1.56
Length-breadth ratio	4.33	4.39	4.82
Grain elongation ratio	1.94	1.95	1.80
Volume expansion	4.00	4.00	3.90
Amylose content (%)	23.52	23.48	22.85
Aroma	Strong	Strong	Mild

Because of its good grain quality and superiority in yield potential, earliness, and short plant height, the State Variety Approval Committee has approved Basmati 385 for general cultivation in the Punjab, India. □

1990 for the Kuban area (Krasnodarsky Territory and Republic of Adygea) and in 1992 for Crimea. It is already planted on 20,000 ha.

The variety was developed by individual selection and biotechnological methods from 40 lines segregated from Krasnodarsky 424 variety.

Krasnodarsky 86 belongs to the japonica subspecies. It is more resistant to lodging, blast, insects, and weeds than Krasnodarsky 424 and is recommended for cultivation without pesticides.